

COMPRESSION STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT ANALYSIS USING DISCRETE DAMAGE MODELING

J. McQuien¹, E. Iarve², K. Hoos³, D. Mollenhauer⁴, M. Flores⁵ and D. Rapking⁶

¹ University of Texas at Arlington Research Institute, jeffrey.mcquien@uta.edu

² University of Texas at Arlington, Dpt. of Mechanical and Aerospace Engr., endel.iarve@uta.edu

³ University of Texas at Arlington Research Institute, kevin.hoos@uta.edu

⁴ Air Force Research Laboratory, Composites Branch, david.mollenhauer@us.af.mil

⁵ Air Force Research Laboratory, Composites Branch, mark.flores.7@us.af.mil

⁶ University of Dayton Research Institute, daniel.rapking@udri.udayton.edu

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ABSTRACT

The Rx-FEM formulation was applied to compression after impact analysis for two experimental configurations. For both configurations, impact-induced damage including permanent out-of-plane deformation, delaminations, and matrix cracks were included into the analysis domain prior to application of compressive loading. While the inclusion of the permanent deformation and delaminations was based directly on provided information, impact-induced matrix cracks were incorporated into the analysis configuration by using the formulation itself and the application of a pseudo-impact load. The resulting matrix cracks matched the accompanying delamination patterns in a consistent and accurate manner. Buckling was predicted for both configurations in the presence of the discretely modeled impact-induced damage. While one configuration matched available experimental results very closely, the other exhibited some disagreement in stiffness response, however matched very closely to experiment in terms of failure strain.

1 INTRODUCTION

The reduction in compression strength after impact (CAI) in composite laminates is an important factor in design and certification of composite structures. Damage resulting from low velocity impact in laminated composites has received extensive investigation in both experimental and simulation based investigations. It is known that damage resulting from a low velocity impact that is visible on the exterior of the laminate does not reflect the extent of internal delamination and cracking, i.e. barely visible damage (BVD). With advances made in nondestructive evaluation methods such as X-ray CT, it is possible to evaluate the extent of BVD in detail. The availability of this description of the impact damage allows for a division of the simulation based investigation of CAI into two independent problems: the first being the task of simulating the impact event, the second being the simulation of the failure of the panel under compressive load after considering a known impact-induced state of damage. The current work is focused on the latter. In order to tackle this problem computationally, the simulation must be able to account for the different types of damage involved, as well as the nonlinear buckling behavior.

The Regularized-Extended Finite Element Method (Rx-FEM) is a discrete damage modeling (DDM) progressive failure analysis method geared towards laminated composites [1]. Rx-FEM models both the initiation and propagation of matrix cracks and delaminations and has been validated in both static and fatigue at the coupon [2][3] and sub-element levels [4]. Recently the matrix crack modeling capability of Rx-FEM was extended to a geometrically nonlinear framework allowing its application to configurations which may undergo large displacements or rotations, or exhibit buckling [5]. With the capability of modeling discrete damage events such as delaminations and matrix cracks in the presence of buckling, and their interaction, Rx-FEM is suited for application to CAI analyses.

This paper will present the application of Rx-FEM methodology to CAI analysis using two experimental configurations. One of the configurations was experimentally investigated at the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), WPAFB, OH. The second configuration was investigated in

detail by Sun and Hallett, considering both experimental and simulated analysis of impact and CAI [6]. As stated previously, this work does not involve the virtual simulation of the impact event, but assumes the impact has already occurred and the state of impact-induced damage is known and available. The discussion will begin with a description of each of the finite element models, including the configurations, material properties, methods of incorporating impact-induced damage into the model prior to the application of compressive load, and boundary conditions. Results will then be presented for each configuration and compared to the available experimental data.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

This section will provide an overview of the Rx-FEM framework and then describe each of the experimental configurations, including geometry, material properties, stacking sequences, considerations made to facilitate the modeling of existing impact-induced damage, and boundary conditions.

2.1 Rx-FEM framework

Rx-FEM is a DDM tool geared toward progressive failure analysis of composite laminates. The framework is available in either an infinitesimal strain formulation or a Total Lagrange formulation for incremental large displacements and rotations. It is built around a mesh independent cracking (MIC) model which allows for cohesive zones, representing matrix cracks, to be inserted during simulation without regard to the finite element discretization. The Rx-FEM technique [1] for MIC insertion is a variant of XFEM, where the traditional Heaviside step function used to represent displacement discontinuities is replaced by a continuous function that is approximated by the finite element shape functions. The approximation of this regularized step function is then able to make use of the native element's original integration scheme. The introduction of this displacement discontinuity is governed by a failure criteria, and the opening of the resulting crack is governed by a mixed mode cohesive zone formulation (CZM). Complementary to MIC, Rx-FEM uses cohesive zones to model the interface between plies in a composite laminate to allow the simulation of delamination, and a continuum damage model (CDM) for capturing the effects of fiber failure. These damage mechanisms are routinely all activated simultaneously allowing for their interaction. In summary the available modes of damage in an Rx-FEM analysis are:

- Intra-ply matrix cracking via MIC
- Inter-ply delamination via CZM
- Intra-ply fiber failure via CDM

The typical Rx-FEM analysis begins with the fragmentation of the analysis domain into clusters, which are independently meshed. Clusters usually fall into different material regions. In the case of composite laminates, each ply is assigned to its own cluster. Each cluster may be enriched for MIC or not, and specified regions within a MIC enriched cluster may be excluded from the enrichment. The latter is usually done to avoid unwanted cracking from occurring near a boundary condition or singularity. These clusters are then connected together to form the full analysis domain by specifying connections. Connections may be either strictly penalty based to maintain displacement continuity, or may involve cohesive properties to allow for delamination. Node-sets on the exterior of each cluster are used to drive the connections. Next, bulk material properties are assigned to each cluster, and cohesive interface properties are assigned to each cohesive connection. When appropriate, these bulk material properties contain strengths to be used in MIC insertion failure criteria, cohesive properties governing MIC propagation, and strengths and trans-fiber toughness governing fiber failure. Lastly, displacement or force boundary conditions are applied to node-sets of the mesh, and load incrementation is prescribed.

2.2 Configurations and material properties

Figure 1: CAI panel configuration

Each of the experimental configurations conform to ASTM standard D7137/D7137M-17 for compression after impact, and were impacted according to ASTM standard D7136/D7136M-15. Following the labels “Configuration A”, and “Configuration B”, and referencing Figure 1, the unique characteristics of each configuration are detailed in Table 1.

Config.	L_x	L_y	t	Material	Layup
A	6 in	4 in	0.127 in	IM7/977-3	$[-45/90/45/90/-45/0/45/90/90/-45/90/45]_s$
B	150 mm	100 mm	4.0 mm	IM7/8552	$[45_2/0_2/90_2/-45_2]_{2s}$

Table 1: CAI configuration details

Ply level material properties are provided in Table 2 for configuration A, and Table 3 for configuration B. These properties include the ply-level elastic properties, the crack insertion strengths, and the strengths and toughness properties of the cohesive zones which govern crack and delamination growth. In addition the analyses conducted herein made use of a CDM model for fiber failure, and so the strength and toughness properties used to govern its behavior are also provided.

IM7/977-3		CZ propagation		MIC insertion		CDM	
E_1 (MPa)	137417	Y_T (MPa)	60	Y_T (MPa)	78.9	X_T (MPa)	3116
E_2, E_3 (MPa)	8694	Y_C (MPa)	200	Y_C (MPa)	240	X_C (MPa)	1567
G_{23} (MPa)	3500	S (MPa)	80	S (MPa)	80	G_{XT}/G_{XC}	80/24
G_{13}, G_{12} (MPa)	5000	G_{IC}	0.25			F_{XT}, F_{XC}	0.2
ν_{23}	0.496	G_{IIC}	0.65			F_{GT}, F_{GC}	0.4
ν_{13}, ν_{12}	0.32						

Table 2: Configuration A, IM7/977-3 material properties

IM7/8552		CZ propagation		MIC insertion		CDM	
E_1 (MPa)	161000	Y_T (MPa)	60	Y_T (MPa)	60	X_T (MPa)	2723
E_2, E_3 (MPa)	11400	Y_C (MPa)	200	Y_C (MPa)	200	X_C (MPa)	1200
G_{23} (MPa)	2980	S (MPa)	95.8	S (MPa)	95.8	G_{XT}/G_{XC}	80/24
G_{13}, G_{12} (MPa)	5170	G_{IC}	0.25			F_{XT}, F_{XC}	0.2
ν_{23}	0.436	G_{IIC}	0.74			F_{GT}, F_{GC}	0.4
ν_{13}, ν_{12}	0.3						

Table 3: Configuration B, IM7/8552 material properties

2.3 Approach to modeling impact damage

It is important to describe the methods by which impact-induced damage was accounted for in the modeling process. The effort of applying Rx-FEM methodology to CAI simulations was divided into two phases. The initial part of the effort pertained to provisioning impact-induced damage into the laminate. This is of course extremely important because the impact damage is what leads to the reduction in compressive strength in CAI analysis. Only after the impact damage was accurately included into the analysis domain was it possible to address the second part of the effort, which was the simulation of failure under in-plane compression. In this work, three categories of impact damage were accounted for. These categories included: permanent out-of-plane deformation that will be referred to as the “dent”, delamination, and matrix cracks. Methods for including these damages will be discussed in the following sections.

2.3.1 Dent

Including the dent into the configuration is rather straight forward. In the case of configuration A, profilometry data of the post-impacted laminate was used to obtain a geometric representation of the surface profile. For configuration B, 3D-DIC measurements of the post-impacted laminate were used to define the surface profile. In both cases, each node of finite element mesh was interpolated, or morphed, onto the surface profiles. The resulting geometry is extremely important for allowing initial instability in the numerical simulation that contributes to buckling.

2.3.2 Delamination

In this work, impact delaminations were provisioned into the configuration by modifying the ply-by-ply cohesive connections based on two different types of information. For configuration A, the source information came from X-ray CT images that were post processed to produce geometric descriptions of the perimeter lines of delaminations on each ply interface. For configuration B, the impact damage sourced into the Rx-FEM analysis was produced by virtual simulation rather than experimental testing. In this case, failed interface cohesive elements from the impact simulation provided the geometric representation of delaminated areas on ply interfaces. In both cases, the available information was used to fragment the node-sets used to specify ply-to-ply connections into either: delaminated or not delaminated. For the delaminated connections, a modified set of cohesive zone properties were used to allow the cohesive zones to open immediately upon loading, and regular properties (Table 2 and 3) were applied to the not-delaminated connections. The delaminated regions were still treated as connections in order to prevent interpenetration. In this way the CAI simulation began with the impact-induced delaminations already existing.

2.3.3 Matrix cracks

Modeling impact-induced matrix cracks was not as straightforward as the dent or delaminations. This is because matrix cracks are not as easily characterized using X-ray CT images. In addition, the matrix cracking patterns needed to be compatible with the delamination patterns. Furthermore, it is known that the delamination patterns produced from impact cannot be simulated without accounting for matrix cracks, or in other words cannot occur without being accompanied by matrix cracking. This means that delamination patterns and matrix cracks are dependent on one another. Since the evolution of the delamination patterns are not being simulated by the Rx-FEM framework, it is seemingly impossible to model matrix cracks into the Rx-FEM analysis configuration in the way that they would be simulated organically by the framework. To elaborate, matrix cracks within the Rx-FEM framework may have varying inclination angles along their path. In the current scope, this complicates scenarios such as a delamination pattern that is bounded by a crack, or a delamination that migrates from one interface to the next via a matrix crack. Both of these phenomena existed in the observed impact damage and were readily observable by visualizing the impact-delamination profiles. Thus the dilemma was as follows: impact-induced matrix cracks were needed that were mathematically compatible with impact-induced delaminations which have been arbitrarily imposed, i.e. not organically simulated by the framework itself.

In the present work this issue was addressed by applying a *pseudo-impact* load during the analysis before applying compression. This means that the Rx-FEM solver was used to simulate the impact-induced matrix cracks in the presence of the imposed impact delaminations. Several modeling steps were taken to accomplish this. First, the finite element mesh, for each ply, was divided into three regions as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CAI finite element mesh regions

The regions were as follows: bulk shown as grey, damage region shown as the green central square, and impact region which is the orange circular area centered in the damage region. The left and right edges which are shaded orange in Figure 2 were not considered a region, but are highlighted to mention that they were excluded from MIC enrichment to prevent cracking due to boundary

conditions. The damage region was sized to encompass the impact-induced delaminations which have been imposed. A set of modified MIC insertion strengths and crack propagation properties was applied to the damage region to facilitate the simulation of the impact-induced matrix cracks during the application of the pseudo-impact loading. The impact region was modeled to facilitate the application of the pseudo-impact, and was sized to reflect the portion of the impactor tip which may come into direct contact with the laminate. On the top surface of the ply on the impact side of the laminate, an out-of-plane displacement was applied to each node within the impact region. This made up the pseudo-impact load. The applied displacement was calculated using a hemispherical function of the radius from the center of the impact region to each node. In addition, an initial displacement was added to prevent severe distortion of the surface near the perimeter of the impact region.

2.4 Boundary conditions and simulations conducted

This section will detail the boundary conditions applied during the compression stage of the CAI analysis. The CAI boundary conditions followed the test fixture detailed in ASTM standard D7137/D7137M-17, which are represented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: CAI boundary conditions

All of the CAI boundary conditions applied were specified displacements, and following what is shown in Figure 3, with the coordinate axes shown in Figure 1 and origin at the center of the panel, these included:

- $u(x = +L_x/2) = u_o$
- $u(x = -L_x/2) = 0$
- $v(y = \pm L_y/2) = 0$
- $w = 0$ along knife edge supports (dotted line in Figure 3, front and back)
- $w = 0$ on clamped regions (diagonally shaded area in Figure 3, front and back)

For each configuration, CAI analysis was performed in addition to a “pristine” panel analysis. In the case of the pristine panel, all of the impact-induced damage was discarded, and the pseudo-impact

loading was forgone. The pristine analyses were conducted to demonstrate a reduction in compressive strength by the presence of impact damage, and to investigate the viability of Rx-FEM in predicting failure of the pristine laminate.

3 RESULTS

The simulation results for both configurations are presented in two sections. First, the inclusion of matrix cracks as part of the effort of modeling impact damage by applying the pseudo-impact load are shown. Then the results of the compression simulations will be discussed. In each section, both the successes and shortcomings of the methodology will be discussed as well as future work to address those shortcomings.

3.1 Impact damage

Results of pseudo-impact modeling are summarized in Figure 4 for configuration A and Figure 5 for configuration B. For each interface the delamination patterns and matrix cracks are shown for selected plies. It is important to note that the delamination patterns shown here are imposed directly onto the analysis configuration, based on the methods described in section 2.3.2, and are not considered simulation results. In each image of Figures 4 and 5, the plies are made transparent so that delaminations, which are shaded red, can be seen on both the top and bottom ply interfaces. The plies are numbered bottom-to-top starting from 1 and increasing towards the impacted side of the laminate. A total of 24 plies were modeled for configuration A, due to the inclusion of a ply interface at the plane of symmetry, and a total of 15 plies were modeled for configuration B where the plane of symmetry was not modeled as a ply interface.

Matrix cracks which were simulated as a result of the methods described in 2.3.3 are colored green. In all cases, matrix cracks were inserted that either bounded the perimeter of a delamination pattern, or connected delaminations migrating from one interface to the other. Several of the plies shown for configuration A lack additional cracks in expected locations, such as in Figures 4b, 4e, and 4h. This may be attributable to crack congestion, where mesh density prohibits Rx-FEM from having available elements to support the insertion of new step functions. However, almost all of the plies shown for configuration B contain the matrix cracks which support the imported delamination patterns. This may suggest crack congestion to not have been the issue, but perhaps the difference of the sources of the information used to import the delaminations. Further investigation will involve mesh refinement studies.

In addition, it can be seen that many cracks extend beyond the delamination patterns, such as Figure 4c, 4d, 5b, 5f, and 5g. This is due to a combination of the use of damage region sectioning, discussed in section 2.3.3 and the way matrix cracks are modeled in the Rx-FEM framework. Because both the crack insertion and opening material parameters were reduced in this damage region, these cracks inevitably open to the boundaries of the damage region (recall the green central region of Figure 2). There are two possible ways to avoid this in future analysis. First, the damage region may be reduced to match the largest impact delamination. This will of course mean that the problem still exists for all other plies which do not contain such a large impact delamination. Another method would involve replenishing the crack opening parameters back to nominal, and increasing the magnitude of the pseudo-impact load. Assuming the same cracks are inserted, this method will require calibration of the pseudo-impact load magnitude to achieve cracks which grow out to, but not beyond, the extent of the impact delaminations.

Figure 4a: Ply 5

Figure 4b: Ply 7

Figure 4c: Ply 9

Figure 4d: Ply 10

Figure 4e: Ply 16

Figure 4f: Ply 18

Figure 4g: Ply 20

Figure 4h: Ply 21

Figure 4: Configuration A impact damage

Figure 5a: Ply 3

Figure 5b: Ply 4

Figure 5c: Ply 5

Figure 5d: Ply 7

Figure 5e: Ply 8

Figure 5f: Ply 10

Figure 5g: Ply 12

Figure 5h: Ply 13

Figure 5: Configuration B impact damage

3.2 CAI failure

Results of CAI analyses for both configurations are organized into a table of key metrics and images of the simulated damage growth in the presence of buckling. Configuration A metrics are organized in Table 4, where the experimental results were provided in the form of MTS load vs. displacement and strain gauge data. The strain gauges were located according to the ASTM standard, and simulated strain measurements were taken from the position corresponding to “Top strain gauge” labeled in Figure 6. For configuration A, there was a significant over prediction of pristine and CAI failure loads. However the failure strains were in close agreement to experiment. Figure 6 plots the strain vs. compressive load for the configuration A CAI analysis. The lower-most curve, labeled “Bottom strain gauge”, represents the strain measured at the same position on the reverse side of the panel and was included to demonstrate the effect of the impact-induced dent.

	Pristine failure (kN)	CAI failure load (kN)	Strength reduction	Pristine failure strain	CAI failure strain
Simulation	127	77	39%	-0.01054	-0.00635
Experiment	89	62	30%	-0.00986	-0.00625
Error	42%	23%	30%	6.9%	1.6%

Table 4: Configuration A simulation results

While a number of reasons could be responsible for the differences between the predicted and experimentally observed failure loads it should be mentioned that a problem in loosening of the fixture at higher load levels, which occurred in all the tests, could be responsible for premature buckling.

Figure 6: Configuration A load response

Key results for configuration B are organized into Table 5, where the experimental data was taken from the CAI experimental observations made by Sun and Hallett for the low velocity impacted specimens of the same configuration [6]. In this case the simulated predictions were in very good agreement with the available experimental results.

	Pristine failure load (kN)	CAI failure load (kN)	Strength reduction
Simulation	181	121	33%
Experiment	175	115	34%
Error	3.4%	5.7%	2.9%

Table 5: Configuration B simulation results

The pristine and impacted panels displayed distinctly different failure modes. The failure of the configuration B pristine panel initiated in the narrow section of the 1/8" unsupported gap section shown in Figure 3 and extended in to the bulk of the plate as shown on Figure 7. Whereas the failure of the configuration B pristine panel amounted to a complete loss of the two 0° plies due to compressive fiber failure. The impacted plates failed by buckling in the damage region. Buckled shapes and damage patterns simulated at the moment just after buckling are shown in Figure 8. In Figures 8c and 8d, the panel is viewed from the impacted side and is made transparent such that all damage through the thickness can be seen. In both cases, the delaminations grew perpendicular to the loading axis, and were accompanied by matrix cracks in the 90° plies. In both cases, very little damage growth occurred prior to buckling.

Figure 7: Configuration B pristine laminate failure profile

Figure 8a: Configuration A buckling profile

Figure 8b: Configuration B buckling profile

Figure 8c: Configuration A buckled damage state

Figure 8d: Configuration B buckled damage state

Figure 8: CAI failure buckling shapes and damage patterns

3.3 Conclusion

Impact-induced damage including permanent out of plane deformation, delaminations, and matrix cracks were incorporated into an Rx-FEM analysis configuration. The Rx-FEM formulation itself was

used to approximately provision the impact-induced matrix cracks using a pseudo-impact load. This offers a workable alternative to processing matrix cracks from experimental images in order to then attempt to include them in the analysis configuration, or placing them manually based on the observed delamination patterns. The method was used for two experimental configurations with varying results. For configuration B, the resulting matrix cracks matched the accompanying delamination patterns well and thoroughly. However, for configuration A, some of the expected cracking was not achieved. It is unclear whether this was due to crack congestion or that the impact-delaminations were captured poorly.

The Rx-FEM formulation was then used to simulate the compressive failure of each configuration due to buckling in the presence of the discretely modeled impact-induced damage. In both cases, buckling was predicted, and in each case at a lower global load than the pristine panel. The predictions for configuration A, which were compared to experimental MTS and strain gauge data, exhibited a failure strain that matched very close to experiment. However, the failure load was significantly different than experiment, which may be attributable to issues that occurred during the experiment, or to a poor stiffness response predicted by the simulation. Configuration B results compared extremely well to the available experimental data in both pristine and impacted panel failure loads. Future work will involve the application of the described methodology to configurations of type B with differing amounts of impact delamination.

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